

Kalundborg
SYMBIOSIS

A Concise Guide to Planning and Implementing Industrial Symbiosis Initiatives

In this guide, we would like to present our recommended approach to planning and implementing circular economy initiatives and transitions in organizations, considering the industrial and cross-sectoral symbioses as one way of implementing circular resource flows. This guide is therefore mostly aimed at companies engaged in manufacturing. This guide is based on our many years of practical experience of building the world's leading industrial symbiosis, Kalundborg Symbiosis in Denmark, as well as on practice-oriented theory from other sources.

The audience for this guide is mostly aimed at decision makers in manufacturing companies who have taken an active decision to change their organizations' operations toward the circular economy and are looking for experience-based guidance on how to get started with this transition.

The guide is concise: we would like to avoid making it into a heavy academic reading, and instead, a practical and useful guide. Some of the larger frameworks we will simply show and refer to the sources, where they can be explained in detail.

Let's start with a couple of definitions, to establish a common understanding of what we are talking about:

Table 1. Green transition and Industrial Symbiosis definition.

What is Green Transition?¹

This is a general term which covers profound changes in our consumption patterns, thereby making this more environmentally friendly. The term can cover structural, economic as well as technological transitions at a societal or a company level. Often the term is used more narrowly to describe the transition from fossil energy to energy from renewable energy sources.

¹ FORCE Technology, [Green business models \(forcetechnology.com\)](https://www.forcetechnology.com)

What is an Industrial Symbiosis?

The key principle of an industrial symbiosis is the physical exchange of materials, energy and water between two or more companies, turning what is normally seen as waste, into a resource.

The companies that collaborate in an industrial symbiosis are often from different sectors, but most often from the same geographical area. By replacing input materials with waste, a company can potentially reduce cost of input materials, while the other company reduce waste disposal costs, and potentially even turns their waste into by-products.

When two companies exchange resources, they have established a symbiotic exchange between them⁹. A network of several individual symbiotic exchanges, where more than two companies are interconnected around more than one resource, is called an industrial symbiosis network.²

Let's get started!

This Guide is built in the following way: in Chapter 1, we discuss the approach we recommend for any company or organization that wants to initiate circular and/or industrial symbiosis initiatives. Meaning that the Chapter 1 is aimed at industrial actors, not at facilitating organizations.

In Chapter 2, we present a framework that we use in our industrial symbiosis building work at Kalundborg Symbiosis. We are a facilitating organization, and we, as well as other facilitating organizations, find the Roadmap presented in Chapter 2 useful. We believe, it will also be a highly useful supplementary tool for the industrial and other market actors, as both a communication tool internally and toward partners, and as a guiding tool as for the steps in the strategic process of building symbiotic relationships.

CHAPTER 1. SYMBIOSIS BUILDING PROCESS FOR INDUSTRIAL ACTORS

Let us reiterate again, that the starting point for the following recommendation is that the management has already taken an active decision to initiate a green transition toward circular economy – meaning that the decision makers in the room do not need to be persuaded of the need for this transition.

When the management team and other relevant decision makers are gathered in the room, the first step is to:

² See Kalundborg Symbiosis' ["Guide for Industrial Symbiosis Facilitators"](#) for further information and inspiration.

1. Understand what circular economy is.

According to the leading resource of knowledge on circular economy, The Ellen MacArthur Foundation: “In our current economy, we take materials from the Earth, make products from them, and eventually throw them away as waste – the process is linear. In a circular economy, by contrast, we stop waste being produced in the first place.

The circular economy is based on three principles, driven by design:

- [Eliminate waste and pollution](#)
- [Circulate products and materials \(at their highest value\)](#)
- [Regenerate nature](#)

It is underpinned by a transition to renewable energy and materials. A circular economy decouples economic activity from the consumption of finite resources. It is a resilient system that is good for business, people and the environment.”

A very good explanation of the circular economy and the elements and approaches in it is shown in the famous ‘Butterfly Diagram’ by The Ellen MacArthur Foundation, which is shown below and explained in a highly instructive manner in the video at the link / QR code below the diagram.

Figure 1 . The butterfly diagram: visualizing the circular economy (ellenmacarthurfoundation.org)

2. Define the ambition for the coming circular economy initiatives or transformation. Start by mapping out your value chain.

It is important to clearly define the scope you will be working within and the ambition that you will be working toward. Is it to find useful application for some of the surplus resources in one of the production lines? Is it to reduce the amount of environmental pollution in one or more lines? Or is it to change the whole business model to work in circular ways?.

To understand the size of the challenge, a highly useful and recommended start is to map out your organization's or relevant business unit's value chain. This will be an exercise of varying complexity for organizations depending on the size, amount of business units, etc. The value chain should be mapped out for that part of business, which the management's ambition is focused on. This exercise is meant to help in defining and specifying the ambition and scope for the circular transformation or initiatives.

Each company's value chain looks differently, and each organization has it mapped out for each of its businesses. Below is a schematic representation of a value chain found in many business textbooks.

Schematic value chain mapping

Figure 2. Schematic value chain mapping.

This exercise is done to define the ambition for, which part of the value chain the current effort should focus on. The ideal that a value chain should aim for in the long term is circularity in use of resources.

This exercise will most probably bring up an active discussion in the decision makers' group, as for where the focus of the coming circular economy activities should be. **It is therefore advisable to put the scope and ambition for the transformation initiative in writing after this exercise is complete, and all the participants agree on the scope and the ambition.**

3. Develop and enact relevant strategic KPIs to ensure correct business case calculation and implementation, in line with the triple bottom line

Many companies today already work with the Triple Bottom Line management system – and the rest should certainly be starting to do so. This is a management system, in which companies are guided not only by the economic profits, but by the social and environmental value that they create.

Whether your firm takes the strategy formulation process full circle with the Strategy Map and Balanced Scorecard or a similar set of tools³, or works with a simplified approach, for example, with clearly formulated strategic objectives and the relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to reach each of the objectives, the new circular approach to conducting business should be measurable and the relevant KPIs should be introduced reflecting the triple bottom line objectives.

Without the proper KPIs, which take the social and environmental aspects into account, business cases for circular economy initiatives cannot be calculated correctly. It is simply not correct or enough to focus only on the financial profits from the planned circular economy and industrial symbiosis operations. From our experience, the farther from the authors of the initiatives the final decisions makers sit (which can e.g. be central management informed by the finance and legal departments), the less engagement in the initiative they will most probably have. They will abide by their usual measurement methods, which are represented by business cases and the KPIs or other decision rules applied for these. **If the environmental and social impacts are not converted into numbers, by which the business cases for new circular economy initiatives are evaluated, they might simply never get a ‘go-ahead’ from the management.**

Below are examples of KPIs for the three aspects of the Triple Bottom Line, which can be used to support an organization’s new green strategic transformation or initiatives. This collection is based on a review of 82 academic articles on the topic. Each organization should select or develop its own KPIs that reflect its own strategic and sustainability objectives, and preferably involve as many of the organization’s managers and relevant specialists as possible in the formulation process – to ensure ownership of and agreement with the KPIs.

³ For the purpose of keeping this Guide short and focused, the Triple Bottom Line Strategy Map and Balanced Scorecard management system are not included here. More information about them is found in all current financial management books, and are summarized in this short article: [Reimagining the Balanced Scorecard for the ESG Era \(hbr.org\)](https://hbr.org).

Figure 3. Environmental, social and economic KPIs. (Source: Hristov, I., Chirico, A. (2019) "The Role of Sustainability Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) in Implementing Sustainable Strategies", Sustainability, 2019, 11, 5742, p. 8, doi:10.3390/su11205742.)

MOVING ON TO WORKING ON INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOTIC VALUE STREAMS

4. Map out geographically close players and resources. Discuss potential symbiotic resource flows and prioritize them.

The local players include organizations, utility companies, other manufacturers and companies in the area, suppliers, municipal authorities, that could be helpful for your organization in re-using or sharing your residual resources with. Possibly, you know of the residual resources that the other players have, which could be useful for your organization.

Discuss, which of the local players your residual resources could be shared with, or which of them have the resources that your organization could use.

This is an extensive exercise, which, if one has not thought of this in advance, will most probably need to be divided into two sessions, where the participants will have time to prepare for session number two with their thoughts on the matter.

Agree on a system to prioritize the proposed resource flows.

In practice, the initiatives will most probably be prioritized naturally, mostly by the desire of the potential partner organizations to collaborate on the initiatives. The symbiotic flows require one or several external partners and investments into infrastructure, transport and other aspects from all the parties. The initiation of each symbiotic resource flow will require strong commitment from the partners to devoting resources to setting the new circular resource flows. In our experience, the participating companies' interest and commitment, is the strongest factor affecting prioritization of the circular economy projects. The larger political, economic and environmental forces can certainly help the prioritization process and the urgency of implementing specific initiatives, i.e. energy-related initiatives at the moment.

Below is an example of symbiosis partners in Kalundborg Symbiosis, a 50-year-old and well-established industrial symbiosis. Its roots come from what Danes simply consider common sense: what is one's company's garbage can be another company's resource. There was no external facilitating organization at the start, as there is today. _____ simply agreed to share their residual resources with one another and built the infrastructure of pipes for it. Kalundborg Symbiosis is now spreading this thinking across sectors, as well as beginning to include SMEs (small and medium-sized companies) into the symbiotic flows.

Figure 4. Kalundborg Symbiosis partners.

5. Establish a dedicated project organization

Transforming a value chain is not an easy task, and a dedicated project organization must be set up. The change WILL NOT happen on its own if no resources are dedicated to conduct the change operation. After the potential industrial symbiotic resource flows have been decided upon in a broader forum with the management, it is time to get to the actual work on making them reality.

Projects need to be calculated as for their triple-bottom-line impact and formulated. Contact to the potential external partners needs to be taken and their interest evaluated, and this will certainly take some time and effort.

After, hopefully, some agreements with external partners are reached, the business cases need to be calculated, negotiated, and if all goes well, agreements need to be signed. Finally, the agreed upon circular economy initiatives – the new resource streams, need to be implemented and communicated.

This is certainly a very short description of a very large piece of work. Yet, if the benefits of the new initiatives are clear for all sides, and once again, the KPIs consider both the environmental, social and economic effects, there is a great and bright potential for the industrial symbiotic flows to be established.

6. Internal communication of the initiatives, creating internal support and excitement

When the initiative's viability is confirmed, it is critical to have a group of internal 'cheerleaders', the famous 'guiding coalition' as is known in the leadership literature, who will help creating excitement and support for the initiatives within the organization. It may be that a local plant's management is excited about a new symbiotic stream, but the legal and finance departments in the head office are more critical. The communication of the benefits of the new initiatives is critical and should not be underestimated – people see the world through the lens of their own profession, hence building internal support for an investment into an industrial symbiotic resource flow in a large organizations is an effort in itself.

7. Agreement and contract negotiation

This step is taken between the individual organizations. The projects will involve investments into infrastructure, evt. transport, legal aspects, from each side, as well as possible negotiation as for lost market shares for certain resource streams, etc. Hence, the companies must find a solution that has a positive business case for each of them. In this regard, choice of the right KPIs to reflect the wins from the upcoming symbiosis and circular economy streams is critical. The KPIs must, besides the financial aspect, measure the environmental impact, impact on the brand image of the company both for the customer and also in various professional fora, as well as possible impact on the local, and even geographically more distant communities, depending on the scope of the initiatives.

8. Implementation

The physical implementation of the new symbiotic streams is conducted by the parties after the detailed agreements are in place. This will most probably include building pipes for fluids (e.g. water) and gasses (e.g. heat, cold air, steam), or organizing other forms of transport for less volatile substances.

9. External communication

Communicating all the reached agreements and important milestones in the implementation, both internally and externally, is extremely important. This inspires the employees in the participating organizations, since they would be able to present to their network that they are a part of a large and positive environment-related change at their workplace.

Furthermore, the initiatives will certainly inspire people and decision makers in other organizations in the area to look up, what is happening and hopefully, consider either joining the newly forming symbiosis if they are located close by, or establish their own. Seeing that their neighbors or maybe even competitors can reach mutually beneficial, symbiotic agreements that favor both our planet and the companies' bottom lines will certainly inspire others to take similar action, together leading to the net positive effect for our common use of resources, for our planet and the communities that the companies are located in.

CHAPTER 2.

KNOWLEDGE SHARING: THE ROADMAP TOOL WE USE AT KALUNDBORG SYMBIOSIS (*a symbiosis facilitating organization*)

The tool presented in this section is found to be highly useful by us and other facilitating organizations in our network. However, we believe that this Roadmap can also be a very useful guide for other actors, e.g., industrial companies that are working on establishing symbiotic value streams with other actors, and therefore it is included in this Guide. The following Roadmap for Facilitating Industrial Symbiosis Partnerships is based on the Symbiosis Readiness Level framework originally developed by Klaus Sommer for the European Commission (2020)⁴. It has been further adjusted by Mie Skjødt in her Master Theses⁵ written at Copenhagen Business School in collaboration with Kalundborg Symbiosis, for a project with Nordic Circularity Hubs. Mie has further developed the framework into the Roadmap, based on numerous interviews with various symbiosis facilitating organizations.

The Roadmap for Facilitating Industrial Symbiosis Partnerships is both useful as a guiding tool through the stages of building symbiotic value streams, and as a communication tool for the potential and actual symbiosis partners, as well as internally in organizations.

Roadmap for Facilitating Industrial Symbiosis Partnerships

Figure 5. SRL – Symbiosis Readiness Level. Model based on Skjødt, 2021.

⁴ Sommer K.H., the European Commission (2020) Study and portfolio review of the projects on industrial symbiosis in DG Research and Innovation, Findings and recommendations, <https://op.europa.eu/da/publication-detail/-/publication/f26dfd11-6288-11ea-b735-01aa75ed71a1>.

⁵ Skjødt, M. (2021) "Symbiosis Readiness Levels: A Conceptual Framework For Facilitating Industrial Symbiosis Partnerships", Master Thesis, Copenhagen Business School, https://research-api.cbs.dk/ws/portalfiles/portal/68331911/1145006_15_MAY_MSS_Master_Thesis.pdf.

The process presented in the stair model is **non-linear**. Iterations between the levels and even going back to earlier levels are a part of the process. Below is an explanation of the activities that each level contains. SRL stands for Symbiosis Readiness Level.

Table 2. Explanation of activities at each level. (Based on Skjødt, 2021.)

Symbiosis Readiness Level	Activities and Results at This Level
SRL 1: The Good Idea	Study prior industrial symbiosis cases for inspiration. Conduct initial mapping of ideas for symbiotic streams.
SRL 2: Local Resources Mapped	In a structured way: Map resources and store information Identify potentially complimentary resources to yours
SRL 3: Screening Completed	Build on known best-case practices. Promote branding benefits and economic prosperity / a positive business case in the initial business plan.
SRL 4: Proof of Concept	Create open dialogue. Build trust and effective knowledge sharing mechanisms with potential symbiosis partners. Establish a collaborative culture.
SRL 5: Sustainability Assessment Finalized	Take a step back and support negotiations by leveraging trust. Leverage branding to build a sense of ownership by the partners.
SRL 6: System Qualified	Focus on placing long-term safeguards for the collaboration to ensure positive Return on Investment.
SRL 7: Partners Committed	Sense of ownership is now transferred to the other companies / symbiosis partners, as well. Issue official press releases on the collaboration.
SRL 8: Commercial Production	Foster informal relationship development and 'gentlemen's agreements' for further development of symbiotic streams.
SRL 9: Resilient Partnership	A well-functioning symbiosis collaboration, where each partner considers potential symbiotic streams in their planning of new industrial activities.